

Work 4.0: The impact of Digital Transformation on Future FET

James T. Morris

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Table of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DT	Digital Transformation
FET	Further Education and Training
VET	Vocational Education and Training
WEC	World Economic Forum

Abstract

Further Education & Training (FET) needs to change. It needs to adapt to new methods of education and is required to deliver and build new skills that we may not even have identified yet (CompTIA, 2012). It needs to prepare learners for new work environments where smart technology, artificial intelligence (AI), automation, data analysis, and virtual / augmented reality are embedded in work & business practices (SOLAS, 2020). FET needs to change or else FET risks becoming irrelevant. Digital transformation (DT) plays an essential role in this change and is identified as a core enabling theme for our FET sector in Ireland, but what exactly does DT mean and what are the requirements and implications for DT in the FET sector in Ireland? What exactly does the FET sector need to do to 'transform' digitally, and how does it need to do it? What are other countries doing to transform and embed technology in education? What do FET institutions in Ireland need to do in relation to digital transformation to remain relevant?

This paper sets out to review literature and research conducted over the past five to ten years in relation to digital transformation in the FET sector across Europe and in Ireland, and to find common themes within the literature, where they exist.

Introduction

The world of work is changing rapidly and is being strongly influenced by social, economic, political, and technological change. In this context, workers are now required to keep pace with these changes in their work and personal lives (World Economic Forum, 2020). Further Education & Training (FET) which has traditionally provided workers with the necessary skills for industry and the workplace needs to change. The sector is required to change quickly to adapt to new curricula and pedagogies suitable for meeting the needs of 21st Century Further, Adult, and vocational educational and societal requirements. FET is required to deliver skilled workers who can work in both the current and future economy and it must also be prepared to deliver programmes for skills that are as yet unidentified (CompTIA, 2012). Learners require the necessary teaching-learning environments that enable them to build on their current competencies and enhance their knowledge, skills, and experience to prepare them for new work environments where smart technology, artificial intelligence (AI), automation, data analysis, and virtual / augmented reality are embedded in work & business practices (Frey and Osborne, 2013). FET needs to change or else FET risks becoming irrelevant (SOLAS, 2020).

This paper presents a literature review of Irish and European research conducted over the past 5-10 years in the areas of digital transformation in FET and is divided into three themes. First, The Future of Work, Industry 4.0 or Work 4.0 as it has been coined. This also includes a review of digital transformation, what this means, and what impact this is having on the types of skillsets required by workers. Second, an examination of the current FET sector in Ireland and the strategy for the coming years. Third, offers a review of FET in Germany, Austria, and Hungary where common themes identified within the extant literature, point to the current focal areas that are driving current European policy with respect to FET. Finally, a conclusion is offered to the overall paper.

Methodology

The approach taken was to research and review publications, journals, websites, and Government reports published within the past five to ten years. The initial decision was to review all available literature within the past 5 years, but it quickly became clear that seminal papers and other publications that related to digital transformation as part of FET strategy both internationally and within Ireland would have to be included. Hence the timeframe 5-10 years.

The focus of the review was to: (a) identify what digital transformation means to further education / vocational education providers across Europe; (b) to understand their approaches to planning for change; (c) to discover what they have done or intend to do to implement and sustain transformation and change across their schemes.

The following literature review is presented under three main areas:

1. Future of Work
2. Current FET sector in Ireland
3. European perspectives, particularly in Germany, Austria, and Hungary

The Future of Work

The world of work is changing rapidly and technological change will have a deep impact on employment, skills requirements, and the future of work (World Economic Forum, 2020). In the first wave of Cedefop's European Skills and Jobs Survey (ESJS) in 2014, it estimated that 14% of EU adult workers were likely to face a very high risk of automation, with the risk of displacement by machines being higher among males and lower-skilled workers (Pouliakas, 2018). According to data collected by Cedefop in the period 2012 to 2015, over 43% of adult employees had already experienced technological change (Cedefop, 2015). Rapid advances in robotics, machine learning, automation and natural language processing are expected to cause enormous societal and economic upheaval over the coming years (Brynjolfsson and McAfee, 2014). Close to half of all jobs (47%) in the US labour market are expected to be changed by automation with the emergence of these new technologies (Frey and Osborne, 2013). According to the OECD in 2019 the pace of digital transformation will be 'startling'. Investments in robotics and artificial intelligence doubled over the period 2018 to 2019, and continues apace (OECD, 2019). This digital transformation happening across the world of work is having a significant impact and requires workers to continuously upskill and prepare for the future. The Fourth Industrial Revolution, or Industry 4.0, is demanding new ways of work and requires workers with new skills. The combination of digital transformation & automation, along with external societal and economic changes will disrupt the world of work over the coming years (World Economic Forum, 2020). According to the World Economic Forum, during the period from 2020 to 2030 over 1.2 billion employees across the globe will be affected by automation and AI. This is equal to 50% of the world economy and affects \$14.6 Trillion in wages (World Economic Forum, 2020). However, predictions by the Forum and others suggest that while the nature of work will change and many jobs will be displaced, overall, the Forum does not expect any more than 5% of jobs to be eliminated.

In their 2019 Future of Work report, the OECD noted technological progress, globalisation, and ageing populations as disruptors of the world of work. While specific forms of jobs or tasks are disappearing, new technologies, business models and worker preferences are creating new forms of

work (OECD, 2019). However, workers will require new skillsets to transition from the roles that are disappearing to the new ones that are being created. At the very least, these skills include digital literacy and computer skills, but in a survey of adult skills conducted by the OECD over the period 2012-2015, 60% of adults did not have any computer experience or lacked basic IT skills (OECD, 2019). They argue that many of these adult learners urgently need to be upskilled or risk being left behind.

In Ireland, the Future FET report (SOLAS, 2020) discusses the ‘megatrends’ transforming the world of work which include Climate Change, Globalisation, an Aging Population, and Digitalisation. According to the report, the EU estimates that 4 out of 10 EU jobs will face transformation over the next few years and the findings of the (Irish) Expert Group on Future Skills Needs back this up suggesting 1 in 3 jobs will be affected by digitalisation. According to the SOLAS report, low-skilled jobs and jobs in administration and customer support will be affected (middle-skill jobs). There are over 300,000 employees in low skilled jobs in Ireland. Surprisingly, given the fact that Ireland supports a very healthy tech sector with all the major technology companies headquartered here, a study by the EUs Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) in 2018 showed that 52% of Ireland’s population did not have basic digital skills (SOLAS, 2020).

Figure 1: Skills and the Future of Work; OECD, 2019.

Source: OECD Employment Outlook 2019: The Future of Work

According to the World Economic Forum, 9 out of 10 jobs will require digital skills in the future, yet 44% of Europeans aged 16 to 74 lack basic digital skills (World Economic Forum, 2020). In 2020 the Forum predicted that by 2025 the ICT industry would have unfilled vacancies of 1.67 million because of the skills gap (World Economic Forum, 2020). The introduction and progress of new technologies will include the automation of low-skilled, routine tasks and require displaced workers to be upskilled (Nokelainen et al., 2018). But what are these new skills, and what types of work will they involve? While it appears obvious that automation and robotics will replace routine tasks, future work will require higher cognitive, problem-solving skills, adaptability, and creativity (Autor, 2015). According to Frey and Osborne, 2013 occupations requiring social or creative intelligence are at a low risk of being replaced by automation. In their 2014 book, *The Second Machine Age*: Brynjolfsson & McAfee discuss how workers with low levels of education and basic or 'ordinary' skills will be replaced by computers and robots, but those highly educated workers with the right skills will be in high demand by companies.

The concept of 'creative destruction' (Schumpeter, 1942) describes how emerging and new technologies will replace many low-level current jobs but will also create new roles which require higher levels of skills. The OECD identifies these skills within the digital areas of automation, artificial intelligence, and mixed reality. The new future workplace will require many highly skilled workers with new and updated qualifications. Workers will require new skills to operate in this new environment and the European FET/VET sector, which plays a central role by providing a skilled workforce, will need to adapt and change by integrating digital technologies into the curriculum.

Digital transformation is another area considered within the literature on the future of work. It is defined generally as the integration of digital technologies into all aspects of an organization's operations, resulting in fundamental changes to how the organization operates and delivers value to its customers or stakeholders (Fürst, 2019). The aim of digital transformation is to realign business models and to improve and develop existing processes (Krcmar, 2018). Recent progress in digital technology is removing constraints and creating exciting new possibilities that affects everyone (Westerman et al, 2014). We have seen from the COVID-19 pandemic that technology can provide workers with a better work-life balance by allowing them work remotely or in a hybrid fashion. These new technologies can also make work safer by utilising automation and robotics to perform jobs that are high-risk or dangerous (OECD, 2019). However, this digital transformation of the business world is creating huge challenges and entails companies managing existing business while simultaneously building for the future (Gupta, 2018). This may involve the adoption of new business models, processes, and strategies that leverage digital technologies to improve efficiency, effectiveness, and innovation (Westerman et al. 2014) which often leads to significant changes in internal operations and processes which companies need to be prepared for (Gupta, 2018).

In summary, it is within this context that FET faces many challenges delivering education and training services and therefore needs to change and adapt to the requirements of providing a skilled workforce who can compete in the future world of Work 4.0 by embracing and integrating technology into its programmes and methods of teaching (SOLAS, 2020). The following section will continue this discussion and take a particular focus on FET in Ireland.

FET in Ireland

The Irish Further Education and Training (FET) sector has evolved from a background of diverse institutions providing technical and vocational training and apprenticeship-style education for learners. While the key objectives of the FET sector are primarily to meet labour market needs and to counteract social exclusion, the sector has traditionally been considered difficult to define and to be at a lower perceived status than Higher Education (McCoy et. al., 2014). Formed from an amalgamation of what were previously called the Vocational Education Committees (VECs) and FÁS, the new further education and training authority was established in 2013 under the name of SOLAS. It is within the context of a changing work environment, the requirement to upskill and reskill workers, and the management of organisational change that SOLAS created their strategic approach to Future FET. This Irish agency (SOLAS) report sets out the national strategy for Further Education and Training for the period 2020 to 2024. It is aimed at transforming learning and is based on three core pillars of building skills, fostering inclusion, and facilitating pathways so that FET is prepared to train and upskill workers and support the economy as it recovers (post-Covid). These strategic pillars are underpinned by four core themes of digital transformation, learner and performance focus, staffing and structures, and capital development (SOLAS, 2020). Currently serving over 200,000 learners with a budget of €800M per annum, the FET sector provides a range of learning opportunities for post second-level education.

The National FET Strategy was developed in a phased approach with the first phase focussing on the current nature of FET provision in Ireland benchmarked against international approaches which included an extensive review of literature and research related to the future world of work. The strategy document comes from extensive research, planning, consultation, and engagement with multiple sponsors, including the benchmarking of international FET systems and strategies. The report focuses on the trends found through consultations with bodies such as the UK Commission on the FE College of the Future with Sir Ian Diamond as Chair, and countries such as New Zealand, Germany, Spain, and Finland. As an example, one of the key trends identified by Finland has been the flexibility in the provision of FE programmes, which includes individualised learning pathways, modular qualifications, and digital solutions (SOLAS, 2020).

The report identifies 4 key areas for the Digital Transformation framework which includes the provision of digital solutions to improve learner access, embedding technology in teaching and learning with the use of virtual learning environments and platforms (VLE), strategic decision-making utilising current databases and sharing data with external partners, and using shared services for management, financial, and other IT services.

Future FET strategic framework (Source: SOLAS, 2020)

Figure 2. Future FET Strategic Framework

Source: SOLAS, 2020; P.13

The implementation of digital transformation in the Further Education & Training (FET) sector provides institutions and practitioners with both opportunities and challenges. As one of the 4 key themes identified by SOLAS in their report Future FET – Transforming Learning (2020), the FET sector acknowledges the need for change and for digital transformation in how they deliver teaching & learning and also in the administration of these programmes. While it is widely acknowledged that embracing and integrating digital technologies into the teaching and learning environment provides benefits to learners such as improved engagement and motivation (OECD, 2015) there are also challenges related to budgetary constraints, organisational and staff change, infrastructure requirements, the digital divide, lack of technical skills (staff), the alignment of technology with pedagogy, and security & data privacy (OECD, 2015). Underpinning this is the requirement of the FET sector to prepare for the future world of education and work and the ability of learners to be able to learn in a flexible and convenient manner, online anytime, from anywhere. Learners need to be digitally enabled, and able to track their learning as they progress (World Economic Forum, 2019). The FET sector in Ireland provides a comprehensive suite of programmes, courses, apprenticeships, and training throughout Ireland to educate, upskill, and reskill learners and workers. Within new

Government strategies and guidelines, FET is expected to make key contributions in the areas of Future Work, Climate Change, and Project Ireland 2040 (SOLAS, 2020). The Future FET report published in 2020 acknowledges the work done to date around technology enhanced learning (TEL), and its use in the pedagogical approach to teaching and learning to date but stresses the need for the FET sector to plan for Digital transformation. It notes three rationales for digitising education as being (a) making better use of digital technology for teaching and learning, (b) the development of digital competences and skills, and (c) the use of data and data analysis to improve educational systems. There is a need to focus on Digital Transformation as a key enabling factor to deliver real reform.

European Overview

Digital transformation is changing the world of work with the requirement for workers to be reskilled and upskilled in digital technologies (Kamsker, S. & Slepcevic-Zach, P. 2021). The Digital Single Market (DSM) initiative adopted in May 2015 by the European Commission is designed to make cross-border online activity more secure and easier to conduct. The initiative requires co-operation between participating states but also, importantly, requires citizens to possess a level of digital skills necessary for inclusion (European Parliament, 2016). The initiative is based on three core policy pillars of improving access to digital goods and services, creating an environment where digital networks and services can prosper, and understanding that digital technologies are a driver for growth (European Commission, 2016).

In 2016, the European Parliament estimated that by 2020 Europe could lack 825,000 digital specialists to complete the DSM, and states that the skill requirements to adjust to Industry 4.0 are much greater than this, meaning there is an enormous challenge in upskilling people for both DSM and Industry 4.0. In short, Digital transformation of the workplace is happening and requires a workforce that is highly trained and skilled to adapt to this transformation. Employees need to be digitally qualified and skilled to prepare for future work and to fully partake in society (Kamsker, S. & Slepcevic-Zach, P. 2021). The Vocational Education & Training sector has traditionally been the main provider of training and skills to the industrial sectors across Europe, and the VET sector needs to change and adapt to prepare the workforce for both DSM and Industry 4.0.

VET in Germany

Digital transformation is changing the world of work, and this requires workers to be reskilled and upskilled in digital technologies. The World Economic Forum reports that 50% of all workers will need to reskill completely by 2025, while 40% of workers will need to upskill their current qualifications by that time (World Economic Forum, 2020). In some parts of Germany, over 86% of highly skilled jobs, especially in digital technologies, remain unfilled because of skills shortages. According to the same study by the World Economic Forum over 2.5 million low-level jobs in Germany will disappear by 2030, however 2.768 million high-level digital jobs will be created (World Economic Forum, 2020). The German VET sector faces challenges in delivering on this and needs to reform its core curriculum, update the digital skillsets of their trainers and teachers, and adapt teaching methods and environments so that digital technologies are embedded in the curriculum and in the delivery of teaching (Yang, C. *et al.*, 2023). VET also needs to appeal more to both young

learners and companies that provide VET training, through information sessions and by further aligning qualifications in VET with Higher education.

In their paper, Yang, C. *et al.* (2023), conduct a study of the challenges that German VET is experiencing in the area of digital transformation and discuss some of the strategies that are being deployed to address them. Again, there is widespread acknowledgement that digital transformation of the workplace is happening apace and requires a workforce that is highly trained and skilled to adapt to this transformation. The study attempts to gain deeper insights into the challenges and strategies for German VET sustaining high quality development in the context of digitalisation and how VET needs to reform and modernise. A theoretical framework is proposed for the sustainability of VET in the digital era which is based on the cooperation between companies and VET schools to address core worker requirements and skills, while also becoming more attractive to learners and companies. While on the one hand German Federal agencies are providing financial support and incentives for companies to promote digital transformation, VET needs to add digital skills and literacy to the curriculum content and upskill teachers and trainers so they can in turn deliver training and education to the learners in these companies (Yang, C. *et al.*, 2023). The challenges faced by VET to improve the digital skillsets of learners is compounded by the lack of digital focus within the curriculum along with a shortage of suitably qualified teachers and trainers. Newer Federal policies however have embedded digital skills within the core curriculum and are addressing the upskilling of teachers. Innovative teaching and learning methods also need to be deployed along with the improvement of digital equipment and infrastructures (Yang, C. *et al.*, 2023).

According to Yang, C. *et al.* (2023), VET needs to cooperate more with companies to address core worker requirements and skills while also becoming more attractive to learners and companies. The perception of a VET education in Germany is not attractive enough to young learners or to companies that provide vocational training. There is an historic image of VET as a 'second-class education' and more young people are now enrolling in higher education courses rather than on courses being run by VET institutions. One of the reasons that medium and small companies in Germany have withdrawn from engagement with VET was the difficulty recruiting suitable applicants. Initiatives are in place from the German Federal Government to make VET more attractive through the provision of quality information delivered face-to-face and digitally, (Yang, C. *et al.*, 2023) and through vocational guidance and career counselling initiatives. Other initiatives include clearly articulating and explaining VET programme contents, entry requirements, examination information, career prospects and levels of income to prospective learners and their parents. Aligning VET more closely with Higher Education and providing pathways between them are also initiatives to make VET more attractive. Ensuring a qualification gained through the VET pathway is equivalent to an academic/university qualification is helping this.

VET in Austria

Digital transformation is bringing greater efficiencies and cost savings to businesses by way of automation, AI, and labour-saving technologies. Some of these technologies will require employees to possess new qualifications and skills while some of the efficiencies created will cause the 'substitution' of some areas of the workforce (Kamsker, S. & Slepcevic-Zach, P., 2021). Employees with higher skills and qualifications are at a lower risk of being substituted than their colleagues with lower skills or qualifications (Kamsker, S. & Slepcevic-Zach, 2021). Essential skills for digital transformation include communications, problem-solving, language, and inter-cultural skills

(Kamsker, S. & Slepcevic-Zach, 2021). In addition to existing skills that an employee may have, it is important for employees to possess these personal and social skills, which are still a differentiator between humans and machines. These requirements for new skillsets and qualifications currently pose a challenge for the vocational educational and training (VET) sector in Austria.

Education providers need to review and amend their offerings to educate future workers and prepare them for the world where digital transformation continues to disrupt. The Digitisation Master Plan of Austria is designed as a guide for schools (in Austria) to adapt teaching and learning to the requirements of digital transformation. This Government initiative addresses three core points which are identified as (i) teaching and learning content, (ii) education, further education, and training of teachers, and (iii) Infrastructure and modern school administration. In the context of business education particularly, core content along with teaching and learning, and specialist subject knowledge must be adapted (Kamsker, S. & Slepcevic-Zach, P., 2021). From a school management perspective teaching equipment, positioning of the school, and partnering with employers are important considerations. In addition, the design and structure of the vocational training system must be reviewed and discussed regarding digital transformation (Ostendorf, 2017). As vocational education and training (VET) is such an important part of the education sector in Austria (78% of the 16-year-old teenagers are engaged in vocational education there) it is important there (and beyond) to change and adapt the teaching and learning methodologies so that learners can be equipped with new skills and qualifications.

VET in Hungary

CEDEFOP, the European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training, conducted a 'Spotlight on VET' report in 2017 which noted a high level of youth unemployment in Hungary coupled with a high degree of skills shortages and a decrease in people enrolling in VET programmes. The report also stated that one third of students were leaving VET without qualifications due to their disadvantaged socioeconomic status and low basic skills (Cedefop, 2017). In their 2019 report, the Hungarian Ministry of Innovation and Technology noted some of the greatest challenges for the VET sector as being a lack of businesses participating in VET as well as lower numbers of learners than in other European countries engaging with VET. The report also mentions deteriorating infrastructure and equipment. The Government strategy at the time to modernise the VET sector was built around three pillars namely, (i) to provide quality infrastructure, such as buildings, classrooms, and workshops, (ii) to produce learners with qualifications and knowledge required by the economy, and (iii) to equip teachers with up-to-date qualifications and knowledge. To address these issues, the Ministry of Innovation and Technology has introduced initiatives such as bridging programmes to equip learners with the basic skills to allow them to participate and succeed in a VET environment. The initiatives also include an easing of progression routes into areas where skills are in high demand and closer links with the employment market resulting in an increase of 74% in apprenticeship enrolment since 2012.

In response to the digital transformation and changing requirements of the labour market, Hungary has developed several digital development projects to prepare its VET sector and its workforce for the future. One of the initiatives is the creation of digital teaching and learning material. The first phase of their 2017 programme had investment by the Hungarian Government of over Eur36 million and ran until 2022. This produced a library of digital teaching and learning

material for use in different VET programmes and fields. The second phase of that programme is currently operational and will run to 2025, with the final phase running until 2027. Overall investment for the three phases of the development is expected to be over Eur133 million (Cedefop, 2022).

	Units for general subjects	Units for vocational subjects	Total number of completed units
Digital learning/teaching scripts	85	227	312
Digital learning/teaching contents	53	226	279

Source: Set up by ReferNet Hungary based on project data (March of 2022).

Figure 3: Supporting Digital Transition of VET

Source: Set up by ReferNET Hungary based on project data (March of 2022)

A second initiative was the development of a knowledge sharing platform for VET teachers which provided them with an easy to navigate, well-structured online platform containing these digital teaching and learning materials. By March 2022 almost 38,000 teachers had registered on the platform. Their final digital project in this initiative was the improvement of digital skills and the development of digital competences for disadvantaged and digitally low-skilled adults in the country. The training and upskilling were designed to provide these adults with initial basic and then more advanced digital skills concerning the internet, emails, cloud solutions, data solutions, and automation. The project which ran from 2015 to 2022 cost over Eur61 million and provided over 264,000 adults with basic and advanced digital training with 98% of those passing the final exam (Cedefop, 2022).

Figure 4: VET in Hungary's Education and Training system

Source: Cedefop and ReferNet Hungary

Common Themes & Challenges

From the reviews conducted on Irish and European literature some common themes were noted such as (i) The future of work, (ii) digital transformation and employee skills, (iii) teaching and learning tools and content, (iv) upskilling teaching staff.

Theme #1 – The Future of Work

The digital transformation happening across the world of work is having a significant impact and requires workers to continuously upskill and prepare for the future (The Fourth Industrial Revolution; Industry 4.0). Automation and robotics will have a significant impact on how we work and what types of work we do. Employees need to be digitally qualified and skilled to prepare for future work and to fully partake in society. Higher cognitive and problem-solving skills are also identified as necessary future skills and the FET sector must prepare for this and be ready to upskill and reskill workers in preparation for the new types of jobs and for the displacement of many current roles.

Theme # 2 – Digital Transformation & Employee Skills

Digital transformation is impacting all areas of work and society and is having an enormous impact on the world we live and work in. Therefore, it is essential that workers are qualified and skilled in digital technologies to embrace and participate fully in this transformation. Digital transformation is bringing greater efficiencies and cost savings to businesses by way of automation, AI, and labour-saving technologies. Some of these technologies will require employees to possess new qualifications and skills while some of the efficiencies created will cause the ‘substitution’ of some areas of the workforce.

Employees with higher skills and qualifications are at a lower risk of being substituted than their colleagues with lower skills or qualifications. Essential skills for digital transformation include communications, problem-solving, language, and inter-cultural skills. In addition to existing skills that an employee may have, it is important for employees to possess these personal and social skills, which are still a differentiator between humans and machines. These requirements for new skillsets and qualifications currently pose a challenge for the vocational educational and training (VET) sector.

Theme # 3 – Teaching & Learning Tools & Content

The design of teaching and learning content and tools such as VLEs is required to prepare learners for Industry 4.0. Vocational Education institutions need to adapt their programmes and curricula as well as their methods of delivery along with upskilling their teaching and learning methodologies to position themselves to deliver these programmes better.

Theme # 4 – Upskilling Teaching Staff

Teachers require upskilling and training in digital technologies and content delivery to keep pace with the changing requirements of digitalisation.

Challenges

Within these common themes there are challenges facing the Further Education and Training (FET) sector in Europe which consist of (a) budgetary constraints and funding issues, (b) lack of digital skills

(staff, teachers) and digital infrastructure, (c) difficulty keeping pace with rapidly changing technologies and learning methods, (d) limited access to continuing professional development (CPD) opportunities for educators, (e) the need for effective collaboration and partnerships between education providers, industry, and other stakeholders, (f) meeting the diverse and changing needs of learners, including those with special educational needs and disabilities, (g) addressing issues of equity and social inclusion, including the digital divide and access to education for disadvantaged groups, (h) ensuring the quality and relevance of education and training programs to meet the needs of the labour market and society as a whole, (i) ensuring the recognition and validation of non-formal and informal learning, and developing flexible pathways for learners to progress through the education system, (j) meeting the challenges posed by demographic changes, including an aging workforce and changing migration patterns.

Conclusions

FET needs to change or FET risks becoming irrelevant. The disruptive nature of the Future of Work or Industry 4.0 and the adoption of automation and robotics will cause the displacement of many types of jobs across the globe; however, many new types of jobs and roles are expected to be created because of new technologies. As a sector that traditionally has had a societal and economic role preparing workers for industry, FET has an enormous role to play. However, FET faces many challenges delivering on this such as outdated teaching and learning materials, tools, and methods, inadequate equipment or infrastructure, and a lack of adequately trained staff with the necessary digital skills.

This paper presents a literature review of Irish and European research conducted over the past 5-10 years in the areas of digital transformation in FET. It examines three core themes which include (i) the Future of Work, incorporating digital transformation, (ii) the current FET sector in Ireland, and strategy for the coming years, and (iii) a review of FET in Germany, Austria, and Hungary. By researching and reviewing papers, publications, journals, reports, and websites published within the past 10 years and related to the area of digital transformation in FET in Ireland and Internationally, a picture of the FET landscape in relation to their challenges and approaches to dealing with them is outlined.

Automation and robotics will have an enormous impact on how we work and what types of work we do. Employees need to be digitally qualified and skilled to prepare for future work and to fully partake in society, yet according to many of the reports, a significant number of employees and citizens in general, lack basic digital literacy skills. Workers need to be upskilled and reskilled to prepare them for the displacement of many of their current roles, and FET has a critical role to play in this. To deliver on this, improved infrastructure along with new tools and teaching & learning methodologies are required. Teachers and FET staff require upskilling and reskilling in the areas of digital technologies, while core curricula, content, and programmes need to change and incorporate these new skills for these economies to remain competitive in the new world of Industry 4.0

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